

Analyzing The Factors Influencing Students' Willingness To Communicate In Speaking Classes At Universitas Negeri Gorontalo

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the psychological and situational factors that influence students' willingness to communicate (WTC) in speaking classes. This study focuses on second-year students of the English Education Study Program at Universitas Negeri Gorontalo who have completed the course "Speaking for Professional Context." Using a qualitative design, data were collected through semi-structured interviews with ten participants selected through purposive sampling. Thematic analysis was used to identify the main themes in the data. The results of the study indicate that both psychological and situational factors significantly influence students' WTC. The most influential psychological factor is self-confidence, while the prominent situational factors include the interlocutor and the role of lecturers. Other prominent themes include learning anxiety, the influence of topic type on perceived communicative competence, classroom atmosphere, and instructor strategies. In practice, these

findings can provide information and strategies for student learning and teaching activities in the classroom.

INTRODUCTION

In general, communication is defined as the process of exchanging information by two or more people to achieve a common understanding. One definition says that communication involves cognitive and affective exchanges between two or more individuals (Numonjonovna, 2021). To create a common meaning in a social context, individuals need communication as a symbolic process of conveying language (Littlejohn & Foss, 2008).

In the context of foreign learning, the process and application of communication has become more complex in various aspects, it is because communication is related to cross-language. One of the important aspects in this case is the negotiation of meaning, as the process of cooperation between speakers and listeners to achieve language understanding, so that there is no misunderstanding of meaning. If a misunderstanding occurs, students who have a high Willingness to communicate will be more courageous to confirm and ask for clarification explicitly so that the information is understood correctly (Xu & Shu, 2024).

In addition, understanding the cultural context is also an important aspect in foreign language learning, where language is part of the culture itself. To learn a foreign language, students must understand the habits, norms, and ways of thinking of native speakers. By understanding that, students will tend to be more comfortable and confident to communicate and will indirectly increase their willingness to communicate (Liu et al. 2023).

Language proficiency is also an important aspect of foreign language learning. Language proficiency includes mastery of vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, etc. it must be possessed by foreign language learners in order to achieve communicative goals (Khen et al. 2021). However, proficiency alone is not enough to practice it. Heidari (2024) said that willingness to communicate (WTC) has a significant role in second or foreign language learners. Students' activeness in the classroom is influenced by their willingness to communicate (Gharibi & Seyyedrezaei, 2016). So it can be said that WTC is a process to guide students to be able to communicate actively using the target language (MacIntyre et al. 1998).

However, research by Wijaya and Rizkina (2022) shows that 72.1% of Indonesian students have low WTC in speaking classes, where some of them have good language skills. The researcher has also found the phenomenon of low willingness to communicate in ELESF students of Batch 2022. This

phenomenon was revealed through an informal discussion between the researcher and the students. Some of them said that they did not have the willingness to communicate in a speaking class, especially in English for professional context. There were times when they were given questions that were quite easy, but they did not want to answer.

Furthermore, they did not dare to express their opinions in the speaking class because they felt shy and afraid of being wrong. The discussion also revealed that although they were active speaking students in high school, they lost that activity when they entered the speaking class. Some students also said that they were quite good at remembering vocabulary, quite familiar with grammar, and pronunciation, but they did not want to practice it for several reasons, such as fear of being wrong, anxiety, lack of confidence, embarrassment, lack of preparation, etc. This indicates that their self-efficacy is very low even though self-efficacy plays an important role in students' confidence to speak in speaking classes. Thus, this preliminary finding shows that WTC is not solely influenced by linguistic ability, but also by psychological and situational factors. This problem should be of concern to all ELESP students and teachers in speaking classes because the purpose of learning to speak cannot be achieved without interaction and communication (Sener, 2014).

In general, the low willingness to communicate in speaking classes is not a new phenomenon. This phenomenon has been discussed by several previous studies, such as research from Tuyen et al. (2019), which stated that willingness to communicate is influenced by two factors, namely psychological factors and situational factors. Another study, also conducted by Prasetyo et al. (2019) explained that the factors that affect willingness to communicate in speaking classes include communication competence, teacher recognition, self-confidence, and classroom environment. Meanwhile, research from Elahi (2016) and Dornyei (2005) highlighted that the factors that influence willingness to communicate in the classroom are individual differences (ID) with other individuals who have different learning processes to achieve speaking learning goals. Differences in individual intentions to use language can affect willingness to communicate (Dewaele & Pavelescu, 2021). This research is also in line with research from Rizka et al. (2023), which states that each individual will adjust their style in different situations.

Research on willingness to communicate has been done several times, however, most of these studies were conducted for school students and located outside Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. Therefore, the researcher seeks to find out the psychological and situational factors that affect the willingness to communicate in ELESP students Batch 2022 at Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. In addition, this research was also conducted based on the phenomenon of low willingness to communicate that occurs in speaking for professional context classes. This research is important to find out how much WTC affects them in the speaking class. In addition, this research can also provide understanding to students and lecturers so that they can both contribute to creating an active and communicative speaking class. The researcher used interview techniques to collect data

RESEARCH METHOD

The method used in this study is descriptive qualitative research. According to Kriyantono (2021), descriptive qualitative research describes data factually, accurately, and systematically, and also seeks to explore data in depth, such as background, factors, or other contextual influences. This approach involves collecting, analyzing, and drawing conclusions based on the data collected.

As stated by Sugiyono (2019), qualitative research is referred to as naturalistic research because it investigates natural phenomena. This research approach was chosen because it aims to produce an understanding of the subject of this study. This study used descriptive qualitative research to analyze psychological and situational factors that influence students' willingness to communicate in class. This study was conducted in the English Language Education Program (ELESP) at Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. The researcher used ten ELESP students from the 2022 cohort as research subjects who would provide their perceptions of the factors influencing their willingness to communicate in speaking classes.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The Factors Influencing Students' Willingness to Communicate in Speaking Classes

Self Confidence

Informant	Quote	Codes
Informant 1	<i>"Pernah...misalnya dengan e ada kak itu pernah saya bicara bridesmaid begitu baru dorang ada komen,,... ("I did...for example, I speak bridesmaid but the pronunciation is wrong so they keep giving comments and laugh,")</i>	Friends often comment and laugh

Informant 2	"... dikarenakan mungkin ada beberapa vocab dan juga grammar yang masih tidak teratur untuk saya berbicara dalam Bahasa Inggris. Selain itu, banyak juga vocabulary yang belum saya kuasai..." (...because there may be some vocabs and grammar that are still irregular for me to speak in English. In addition, there are also many vocabulary that I have not mastered ...)"	Lack of vocabulary and grammar
Informant 8	"... saya belum menguasai topik atau materinya samsek kak krna sy belum prsiapkan ... (...I didn't master the topic or the material because I hadn't prepared it yet...)"	Lack of preparation
Informant 7	"... kalau dosen meminta saya untuk bicara kayaknya saya jauh lebih PD kalau saya disuruh bicara oleh dosen ketimbang bicara sesuai kemauan sendiri kak ... (it seemed that I was much more confident if I was told to speak by the lecturer rather than speaking according to my intention)"	Increase if lecturers actively involve students in the class
Informant 3	"...karena melihat skill speaking teman udah di atas..." (...because I see that my friend's speaking skills already above")	Friend's speaking Skill

Based on the above schematic, there is a pattern of factor confidence that is most often mentioned by the informant. Informant 1 experiences self-doubt when speaking in class due to the influence of friends who make comments and laugh when there is a mispronunciation.

According to the informants, the lack of *vocabulary* and *grammar* caused them to lack confidence in speaking, so they were hesitant to speak in class for fear of making mistakes. Informant two said that he often mixes the use of English and Indonesian when speaking in class because of the lack of *vocabulary* he has. In line with Informant 2's statement, Informant 4 also said that her lack of *vocabulary* caused her to feel insecure and nervous when she had to speak English. However, this will be reduced if she is in a class with a relaxed lecturer. In addition to the lack of knowledge in English, the lack of preparation before the class starts can also affect confidence in *willingness to communicate*.

From the results of the interview, it can be seen that the factor of confidence does influence their willingness to communicate in the classroom. Lack of confidence has hindered students' willingness to communicate. In the interview, some informants also revealed things that made them feel more confident when communicating in class.

Based on the above schematic, most of the informants expressed their confidence increased when lecturers asked questions and gave presentation assignments in front of the class. Their self-confidence will increase if they are under pressure. This self-confidence will also increase if the atmosphere in the classroom is supportive. For example, friends are not easily laughed at when they make mistakes. For some informants, confidence has a major role in increasing their *willingness to communicate*. Therefore, they will force the confidence to arise in them to speak in class.

Based on the data, self-confidence can be a factor that affects their willingness to communicate. Their confidence is influenced by friends, lecturers, vocabulary mastery, grammar, and lack of self-preparation. Friends and lecturers are the reasons most often mentioned by students.

Friends can have both positive and negative influences on students' confidence, while pressure and encouragement from lecturers can motivate students to be confident in communicating in speaking classes.

Perceived Communicative Competency

The Codes of Perceived Communicative Competency Interview

Informant	Quote	Code
Informant 3	" Kalau untuk kemauan berbicara itu saya rasa tergantung situasi kak, jadi saya memberi nilai terhadap WTC saya 8 per 10 (As for the willingness to speak, I think it depends on the	Situationally-Driven WTC Supportive class

	<i>situation , so I give my WTC a score of 8 out of 10)"</i>		
Informant 6	<i>"... yang torang butuhkan untuk willing to speak itu karna situasi dan lingkungan pembelajaran yang selalu support...." ("... what we need to be willing to speak is because of the learning situation and environment that always supports us....")</i>	environment communicative competence	boosts

Based on the results of the interviews, it can be seen that some informants rated their communicative competence above 6, but some of them gave lower ratings than speaking and other skills. It can be highlighted that the speaking ability of some students is not the same as their willingness to communicate. They have lower willingness to communicate than their speaking knowledge, which means that their speaking ability is not directly proportional to their willingness to communicate

Based on the data, communicative competence can also influence students' WTC. On average, students rate themselves above 6 out of 10 for their communicative competence. Some students have no reason, but others give reasons that their communicative competence score depends on the situation in the classroom and their experiences in every semester. If the classroom situation makes them feel comfortable and not stressed, their communicative competence score can increase, and vice versa. Thus, their willingness to communicate can also be influenced by their communicative competence.

Learning Anxiety

Table 6

The Codes of Learning Anxiety Interview

Informant	Quote	Code
Informant 4	<i>"Kalau ini sering-sering kak,saya gugup...." ("I'm often nervous")</i>	Frequently experienced
Informant 3	<i>"...pressure dari teman paling tinggi Karna pressure di dalam kelas yang membuat saya tertekan...."("... The pressure from my friends was the highest. Because of the pressure in the classroom, I felt depressed....")</i>	Pressure from friends
Informant 1	<i>" Sering kak. Karna tidak ada kosa kata kak. kurang sekali kosa kata ... "(I often felt that, because I don't have vocabulary, I don't have a lot of vocabulary....")</i>	Limited Vocabulary

From the interviews with the four informants, it can be seen that they often experience speaking anxiety when they are in a speaking class. One of them even showed symptoms of dizziness and nausea. This is caused by the pressure they feel from their friends and lecturers, which makes them feel anxious and worried. From the results of the interview , it can be seen that almost all informants experience anxiety in the classroom, and only one does not feel it. The factor most mentioned by the informants was the influence of friends who laughed and corrected. Lecturers who brought tension could also affect the informants' anxiety. In addition, there were other factors that influenced some informants. such as lack of English vocabulary, self-awareness of appearance, and lack of preparation for the topic discussed in class.

Personality

Table 7

The Codes of Personality Interview

Informant	Quote	Code
Informant 3	<i>"Nah menurut saya itu sangat berpengaruh..."(well,I think it's very influential...")</i>	Personality can influence
Informant 5	<i>"Menurut saya kepribadian itu tidak berpengaruh..."("In my opinion, personality perceptions of</i>	Divergent perceptions of

<i>has no effect...")</i>	personality influence
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According to the five informants, personality does not influence the willingness to communicate. Informant 2 and Informant 9 have experience with introverted friends but are more willing to communicate in a larger class than extroverts. Meanwhile, Informant 5 said that other things, such as confidence, class situation, friends, and the desire to learn, have more influence on the willingness to communicate compared to the willingness to communicate owned by students.

The same thing was also conveyed by Informant 6, who said that willingness to communicate depends on a person's willingness to speak or not in class, not personality.

Conclusions: From the results of the interview, it can be concluded that some informants think that personality has a significant effect on willingness to communicate, while some other informants do not see this influence. Those who argue that personality does not affect willingness to communicate see that many other things are more influential, such as self-confidence, class situations, and willingness to speak in class. The informants also argued that they had friends who were introverted, but were more active and showed a higher willingness to communicate than extroverts.

Situational Factors

Table 8

The Codes of The Influence of Task Types

Informant	Quote	Code
Informant 9	<i>"To be honest,itu tidak ada pengaruhnya sih kak,sorry ya kak...."("To be honest it has no effect,I'm sorry....")</i>	Less impact
Informant 2	<i>" Untuk tugasnya sendiri,saya rasa tidak terlalu memberikan dorongan untukmeningkatkan kemauan dan kemampuan berbicara Bahasa inggris..."("For the task itself, I don 't think it gives too much encouragement to improve the willingness and ability to speak English")</i>	Influential, but only slightly

Seven out of ten informants revealed that the task did not help their communication skills or make them willing to communicate in the classroom. Informant 2 said that the assignments given by lecturers tend to be simple videos that are done per group, so that they only require a small part of each student. It does not influence his willingness to communicate at all. The same was felt by Informant 10. However, Informant 7 said that the assignment given by the lecturer can provide new insights about vocabulary in English, although it still does not encourage a willingness to communicate. For the seven informants, the tasks did not succeed in increasing their activity in the classroom. On the other hand, the other three informants felt that the task helped a little in their ability and willingness to communicate in class.

Based on the results of the interview, it can be concluded that most students do not feel that the task can influence their willingness to communicate. Only a small percentage of informants felt that assignments affected their willingness and communication skills in class.

The Influence of Topic

Table 9

The codes of The Influence of Topic Interview

Informant	Quote	Code
Informant 2	<i>"...kebanyakan mahasiswa itu lebih suka yang umum-umum nah jadi mungkin topiknya lebih umum saja..."("...Most students prefer general topics, so maybe the topic should be more general...")</i>	General and familiar topic more interesting

Based on the data obtained through interviews, the researcher found that topics that can influence students' willingness to communicate are common and familiar topics, such as topics about themselves, hobbies, etc. According to the results of the interview, most informants consider topics that are general and familiar to be easier to understand and can encourage their willingness to communicate in class. However, there is informant consider that preparation is more important, regardless of the topic of discussion.

Role of Lecturers**Table 10***The Codes of Lecturer Role*

Informant	Quote	Code
Informant 1	" <i>Berpengaruh sekali,ada dosen yang sering kasih saya semangat dan kasih-kasih kasih jurnal</i> "(<i>"It is very influential, there are lecturers who often give me enthusiasm and love for journals...."</i>)	Lecturer has an influential role
Informant 10	" <i>...dosen yang sering memuji dan mengapresiasi itu bikin saya bahagia sekali kak sumpah.</i> " (<i>"...the lecturers who often praise and appreciate me make me very happy, I swear."</i>)	Give appreciation and a compliment
Informant 5	" <i>...dosen sering kasih motivasi</i> "(<i>"...the lecturer often gives motivation..."</i>)	Lecturer as a motivator

Many informants said that lecturers have an important influence on students' willingness to communicate. Lecturers act as motivators who often also give appreciation and compliments to their students. In the view of the informants, lecturers have an important role in the classroom. Informant 1 said that the lecturer who gave words of encouragement at the end of the lesson and journal materials had given him encouragement in his willingness to communicate.

Based on the results interviews above, it can be concluded that lecturers have a role as motivators and mentors for the informants. Three out of 10 informants considered lecturers to be the factor that most influenced their willingness to communicate in class. Lecturers play a role in creating an interactive classroom situation so that students are encouraged to be more active. Lecturers also play an important role in improving students' understanding of lessons so that their willingness to communicate increases.

Classroom Atmosphere**Table 11***The Codes of Classroom Atmosphere Interview*

Informant	Quote	Code
Informant 6	" <i>... kalau suasananya santai pasti bikin nyaman belajar tapi kalau tegang ya pasti bikin tidak nyaman.</i> " (<i>" ... if the atmosphere is relaxed, it will make us comfortable studying, but if it's tense, it will make us uncomfortable ..."</i>)	Relaxed And a comfortable class
Informant 10	" <i>... situasi yang bikin saya nyaman dimulai dari pengaruh teman yang positif dan peran dosen kak.</i> " (<i>"...the situation that makes me comfortable, starting from the influence of positive friends and the role of the lecturer."</i>)	Supportive friends and lecturer

The four informants assessed that the tense classroom atmosphere could reduce the students' willingness to communicate. To increase the willingness to communicate in the classroom, students need a relaxed and comfortable classroom atmosphere to study. This cannot be separated from the role of lecturers and other students in the classroom. Another informant revealed that active friends tend to liven up the class more and encourage them to be actively involved in classroom communication.

Based on the interview, it can be seen that the classroom atmosphere is considered to be influential in the willingness to communicate in the classroom. The atmosphere in the classroom is comfortable, relaxed, supportive lecturers and active students tend to increase the students' willingness to communicate. On the other hand, a tense classroom atmosphere, lecturers and students who are passive or silent tend to make students also become passive in communicating. The informants also added that friends are the main factor that makes them feel comfortable and not tense in class, so their willingness to communicate is more improved than in class with friends who like to interrupt their conversations, laugh and make fun of them.

Based on the interview, it can be concluded that a positive classroom atmosphere with supportive friends makes all informants feel more comfortable and increases their willingness to communicate. In addition, some informants also said that friends who had prepared themselves before the lesson started motivated them and made them feel more prepared in class. Meanwhile, friends who like to laugh and mock make the informants feel tense in the classroom, so they are reluctant to communicate in class.

Interlocutor

Table 11

The Codes of Interlocutor Interview

Informant	Quote	Code
Informant 2	" <i>Iya berpengaruh juga kak, kalau dengan teman sendiri itu saya terbantu untuk meningkatkan kemauan untuk berkomunikasi...</i> " ("Yes, it also influences, if with my own friends, it helps me to increase my willingness to communicate...")	influential
Informant 6	" <i>Yup bisa dibilang berpengaruh cukup besar kak karna kadang saya bantu teman juga kalau disuruh jadi mitra bicara karna torang bisa saling membantu dalam hal speaking kak...</i> " ("Yup, you can say that it has a big influence because sometimes I help my friends too if I am told to be a Interlocutor because we can help each other in terms of speaking...")	Supportive friends
Informant 5	" <i>Menurut saya mitra bicara di kelas itu punya faktor besar terhadap willingness to communicate...</i> " ("In my opinion, the speaking partner in the class has a big factor in the willingness to communicate")	The interlocutor has a big influence

All informants stated that having friends as interlocutors has an important role in influencing their willingness to communicate, with varying reasons. According to the informants, friends as talking partners can increase the willingness to communicate.

From the results of the interview, it can be seen that the Interlocutor can support, Interlocutor plays an important role in increasing the willingness to communicate. Friends as talking partners are seen as motivators and tutors who can provide *feedback* in interactions. The skills of a higher-level speaking partner can also motivate students to reach the same level. The Interlocutor acts as a place to learn in a relaxed and comfortable way so that it can motivate the willingness to communicate. Some informants also added that friends are the biggest factor that most affects their willingness to communicate.

Based on the results of the interview, it can be concluded that the Interlocutor significantly influences the informants' willingness to communicate in English. A conversation partner who is relaxed and comfortable to talk to and does not easily laugh or comment on their mistakes can increase their willingness to communicate in English. The interlocutors are considered supporters of their learning process, so that they are motivated to improve their knowledge and communication skills. The majority of informants even consider the Interlocutor as the most influential factor in willingness to communicate because the Interlocutor is willing to help each other and provide feedback for them.

Lecturer Strategy

Table 11

The Codes of Lecture strategy Interview

Informant	Quote	Code
Informant 3	" <i>Menurut saya strategi dosen berpengaruh ke WTC ya kak...</i> " ("I think the lecturer's strategy has an influence on WTC...")	Lecturer's strategy influences WTC
Informant 1	" <i>... jangan cuma materi-materi terus. iya sih kaya tidak masuk akal kalau dosen mencari tau apa kemauan-kemauan setiap mahasiswa.</i> " ("...don't just keep the materials but lecturers find out what the need of every student...")	Interactive and student-centered learning

Informant 5	" Saya setuju lebih ke role play begitu kak karna saya rasa itu bisa meningkatkan willingness kak ("I agree more with role play because I think it can increase your willingness.")	Role play as a preferred learning model
Informant 6	" Saya harap sih lebih bisa menciptakan suasana kelas lebih asik lagi dan tidak ada pressure mungkin perlu ada games begitu " ("I hope it can create a more fun classroom atmosphere and there is no pressure, maybe there needs games ... ")	Creating a fun and pressure-free enviroment

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The data above can be concluded that the learning strategies applied by lecturers influence students' willingness to communicate. Some informants emphasized the importance of implementing fun learning methods, not just lecturers providing material. Interesting learning strategies, such as role play and active talk, can be applied by lecturers in the classroom. Both learning models are considered to make students more active and have more space to engage in communication in the classroom so that they have the willingness to speak more in class.

Based on the results of the data analysis above, the researcher found that the psychological factor that most affected the willingness to communicate with the informants was the aspect of confidence. Informant 4 and Informant 5 even forced themselves to develop confidence when they did not have a good understanding of English. They chose to mix English and Indonesian to still be able to communicate in the classroom with a basic level of English comprehension, Informant 6 also did the same and added the practice of speaking English with friends in daily life to improve their English skills.

The researcher also found that the most influential situational factor on the informants' willingness to communicate was the aspect of the interlocutor. 6 out of 10 informants assessed that their speaking partners can improve their speaking skills and willingness to communicate, both inside and outside the classroom. A pleasant conversation partner, not easy to comment on and laugh at the mistakes they make can encourage the emergence of a comfortable learning atmosphere so that they are more confident in communicating.

Furthermore, lecturers occupy the second position, which is considered to greatly affect students' willingness to communicate. Lecturers act as motivators and mentors who can increase students' willingness to communicate. Lecturers are considered to play a big role in making the classroom environment or situation more active, which affects student communication in the classroom.

Discussion

Complementing this, Tuyen et al.(2019) described 2 factors that influence students' willingness to communicate in the classroom, namely psychological and situational factors.

Psychological factors

According to the second layer in the WTC pyramid by MacIntyre and Wang(2021), psychological factors play a role in determining the extent to the which a person is motivated and comfortable to speak or interact verbally. Studying this psychological factor is important to describe, predict, and manage the

psychology and behavior of students in communication. Psychological factors that influence students' willingness to communicate are self-confidence, perceived communicative competence, learning anxiety, and personality.

First, self-confidence. Tuyen et al. (2019) emphasize that self-confidence is one of the most dominant psychological factors in WTC. This study supports the fourth layer of the WTC pyramid proposed by Maclyntire and Wang (2021), which states that self-confidence is a crucial factor in readiness to communicate, especially in foreign language classes.

This indicated that the study aligned with the interview, where informants who are students of the English Language Education Study Program Class of 2022 revealed that self-confidence has an important influence on their willingness to communicate. They felt that they did not have good English skills, so they often made mistakes when speaking. They also have classmates who tend to comment on and laugh at their mistakes during class. These mistakes are sometimes made into jokes outside of class, which makes the informants feel embarrassed and reluctant to communicate during lessons.

In addition, low self-confidence also arises due to the lack of experience, *vocabulary*, and *grammar*. This is in line with research conducted by Halid et al. (2022), which shows that English language learners face various challenges when participating in IELTS-based speaking exercises. These challenges include difficulty in formulating answers, lack of academic vocabulary, and concerns about grammatical structure. These findings indicate that when students feel incompetent, they are reluctant to speak.

They also do not master the topic of discussion, and the lack of preparation before class can also reduce students' confidence. This lack of confidence causes students to feel incapable and reluctant to speak English in class. This lack of confidence also significantly affects other psychological factors, namely communicative competence assessment and anxiety. This result aligned with Suryadi (2018) disclosed that the vocabulary has a significant effect on students' self-confidence and speaking skills. Another study on self-confidence was also reviewed by Kartika (2018) stated that students who feel less confident due to limitations in grammar and speaking experience tend to be reluctant to participate in class.

This result is supported by research from Chiado and Malave (2024), which stated that 8 out of 10 students have a bad experience with unsupportive learning groups. Aligned with interview results, which revealed that an unsupportive classroom environment will have a significant effect on student self-confidence.

It can be concluded that self-confidence has an important role in willingness to communicate, as cited by Maclyntire et al. (1998), who stated that self-confidence plays an important role in individual communication skills. Students can communicate well if they have high self-confidence. Conversely, students will have low communication skills if they have low self-confidence to communicate. Students who have low self-confidence tend to be reluctant to speak in English in class, especially if they have had bad communication experiences like being laughed at when they are wrong in pronunciation, as felt by some informants. Therefore, students need to increase their confidence. For example, by preparing themselves before class starts, practicing English skills in daily life with friends, and setting a good grade as a target that students will be more motivated to actively engage in classroom communication.

Second, Perceived Communicative Competence is a concept in the WTC model. Students self-assess their communicative competence using English in the classroom. Based on the analysis of research data, researchers found that most informants had an average self-assessment above 5 out of 10. Some informants also said that their speaking communication skills in the classroom were inferior to other skills. Meanwhile, Most informants indicated that their perceived communicative competence depended on the situation in the classroom, where they felt a positive value perception when the classroom atmosphere was relaxed and comfortable. The same theory was also put forward by Maclyntire et al. (1998), who stated that a lack of confidence can inhibit an individual's willingness, causing them to place low marks on their perceived communicative competence.

This result agreed with a study, as cited by Leming et al.(2024), who stated that PCC has a direct predictive impact on students' willingness to communicate. PCC is closely related to student motivation. Students can be motivated to talk because they are in the right and safe environment. This finding aligned with Spitzberg et al. (1984), who stated that the perception of communicative competence comes from the situation and motivation of individuals in communicating. In addition, skills are also an important aspect of the perception of communicative competence. This is why Informant 1 felt that her perception of communication competence was increasing as the semester went on.

Third, Learning anxiety. Based on the analysis of research data, this study found that informants had factors that caused them to feel anxious when communicating in class. This is supported by Petrova (in Zulfikar 2022), who stated that anxiety in communication is anxiety in expressing ideas, feelings, and opinions to others, including anxiety about acceptance caused by various psychological factors. Most

informants felt the same anxiety, and there was even an informant who experienced symptoms such as sweating, dizziness, and nausea. This informant's statement is in line with research conducted by Machmud and Abdulah (2017), which showed that EFL students often exhibit symptoms of anxiety such as sweating, trembling, and panic when asked to speak directly in class, which significantly reduces their participation in oral communication, while other informants were worried about mistakes in pronunciation or other things, such as vocabulary and minimal practice. This is aligned with research by Mentari et al. (2023), which indicated that anxiety in speaking English is influenced by limited vocabulary mastery and low exposure to oral communication practices.

They experienced anxiety about receiving negative judgments from their classmates, which were then used as jokes and laughed at. Weda et al. (2021) also support that one of the factors causing anxiety is a lack of confidence in their abilities. This is in line with the results interview, which indicated that this type of anxiety is felt by some informants who feel anxious if they do not master the topic of conversation. This level of anxiety significantly influences their willingness to communicate, especially in a foreign language. Therefore, informants tend to become passive in class when they feel anxious.

Fourth, according to several previous studies, personality is an important component that affects the willingness to communicate owned by students (Riasati, 2012). Based on the research interview, the study found that five out of ten informants assessed that personality did affect the willingness to communicate. They argue that students with extroverted personalities are more likely to be actively involved in the classroom than students with introverted personalities.

This finding aligned with the results of a study by Bergil (2016), which showed that extroverted students at Amasya University in Turkey were more successful in speaking well in front of class than introverted students. However, based on the research results, it was revealed that some informants stated that personality does not affect their willingness to communicate. This is because they have friends who have introverted personalities and are more active in communicating in class compared to extroverted students. This indicated that the research finding agrees with Retnoningrum (2022), who said that individuals with extroverted personalities are not necessarily better communicators than introverted personalities.

Situational Factors

According to Fadilah (2018:176), the social and classroom environment can motivate students to communicate voluntarily in the classroom. Studying situational factors in their influence on willingness to communicate is expected to explain how students and lecturers can adapt to different classroom situations.

There are several situational factors, as cited by Tuyen et al. (2019), include the type of assignment, the topic of discussion, the role of the lecturer, the classroom situation, speaking partners, and the lecturer's strategy.

First, the influence of task type on willingness to communicate in a speaking class. Assignments are learning activities that aim to develop structural knowledge or communication skills. Based on the results of the study, seven out of 10 informants revealed that the assignments given by lecturers in the Speaking for Professional Context class did not influence their communication skills.

This result contrasts with Aubrey (as cited in Toyada et al. 2021), who stated that assignments have a potential role to increase students' willingness to communicate from a situational factor.

The researcher also captured statements implying that two informants did not like the video speaking task done in groups. They preferred to do the speaking task alone without having to share speaking parts with other members. Research related to video tasks has been conducted by Machmud and Abdulah (2018), who found that students taught using mobile phone applications showed significant improvements in speaking. Through features such as voice recorders and video projects, students are given space to express their ideas independently and creatively without direct social pressure in the classroom.

It can be concluded that the informants did not like group tasks because they could limit their speaking and their communication skills did not improve. However, this finding contradicts Latifah's (2020) research, which states that tasks that can influence students' willingness to communicate are tasks related to pair activities, group projects, and individual presentations.

From this finding, there is an important point that needs to be highlighted that it turns out that the assignments given by lecturers do not affect the willingness to communicate of ELESP students Batch 2022 in speaking for the professional context class. This is worth discussing because generally, assignments are very important for students to measure the extent of their understanding while learning in speaking classes, but ironically, these assignments do not have any effect on their willingness to communicate. This can be the material for further research to find out more about students' perspectives on assignments, especially in speaking classes.

Second, the influence of the topic. This study found that 9 out of 10 informants considered the topic of discussion to influence their willingness to communicate in class, especially when lecturers discuss topics that they are good at, such as hobbies and viral news. All informants' opinions are aligned with Favero (as cited in Weda et al. 2021), who stated that the majority of students are willing to talk in a discussion group if the topic is interesting. This is also aligned with Barjesteh et al. (as cited in Weda et al. 2021) revealed that EFL learners in Iran are willing to start communication when they are familiar with the topic of study.

Third, the lecturer role includes actions taken in the classroom, such as providing clear explanations, providing feedback or encouragement, and creating opportunities for students to engage in conversations. Based on the research results, all informants stated that lecturers have a vital role in presenting students' willingness to communicate in the classroom. This is aligned with Latifah et al. (2020), which showed that for 77% of students, the role of teachers was very influential in their willingness to communicate. This makes lecturers a crucial factor in the willingness to communicate through the initiation of teachers in teaching and providing material in class. Mardiana and Afkar, (2020) This finding also aligned with the results of Cao (2011), which found that when students like the role of their lecturers, they tend to participate during the class actively. This study proves that 9 out of 10 informants view lecturers as motivators, encouraging students. This study align with the interview high revealed that the role of lecturers is the situational factor that most influence their willingness to communicate because lecturers can carry out various roles, such as motivators and fun mentors, it has a positive impact on their active communication in the classroom.

Fourth, the classroom atmosphere refers to the emotions, moods, or environment in the classroom that reflects the involvement and participation of all its members. According to Tuyen et al. (2019), a friendly classroom situation can increase students' willingness to communicate, while a boring and passive classroom atmosphere can decrease students' willingness to communicate. This is aligned with Okabaashi's research (2024), which conducted research on EFL students in Japan. The results of the study stated that the classroom atmosphere is one of the important factors that can affect students' willingness to communicate.

This indicated that their findings support the results of this study, which revealed that ELESP students batch 2022 wanted a relaxed classroom situation, friends who actively participated, and who did not easy to laugh at other friends' mistakes. Some informants emphasized the importance of a relaxed class, while other informants emphasized that friends who are active in the class are influential in increasing their willingness to communicate. A relaxed, comfortable, and filled classroom atmosphere filled with students who are actively involved in learning will encourage other students to be actively involved in the classroom as well. On the other hand, a tense classroom atmosphere, dominated by students who tend to be silent, will reduce the willingness of other students to communicate in the class.

Fifth, interlocutor. In this stage, the study found that some ELESP students batch 2022 tend to be more comfortable and open in communicating using English with friends and friends who are not easy to blame or laugh at their mistakes in communicating. Another informant mentioned that the characteristics of an interlocutor is willing to help each other, do not hesitate to give *feedback*, and provide comfort in communicating are talking partners who can improve their language skills. This finding aligns with Mahdi (2015), who revealed that 70% of students are willing to initiate conversations with friends.

Based on the interview, It can be said that students are more comfortable when talking with friends than talking with lecturers. This finding aligned with Riasti and Rahimi's research (as cited in Azwar & Harahap, 2021), which found that many students were less willing to talk to lecturers because of fear and reluctance. This finding is also supported by Loh and Teo's research (as cited in Azwar & Harahap, 2021), which states that students' passivity and fear of lecturers stem from the collectivist culture commonly adopted by Asians, which considers lecturers to be authoritarian figures. This makes students participate less in class and feel more comfortable talking to peers than lecturers.

Therefore, all informants are interested in communicating using English with these friends. Although there is a possibility that their speaking partner has a higher language level, the informants do not feel insecure as long as the Interlocutor has these characteristics. The informants will feel motivated to reach the same level as the talking partner. Six out of 10 informants also answered that their interlocutor friend is the biggest factor that affects their willingness to communicate the most.

Sixth, the application of the right strategies by lecturers can increase their willingness to be actively involved and communicate in class. According to a study by Kuutila (2014), approximately 78 percent of respondents stated that the teaching strategies used by English as a foreign language (EFL) teachers positively influenced their willingness to communicate in English. The study is alined with Wijaya (as cited in Khoudri, 2024) stated that the methods and strategies used by lecturers increase the willingness to communicate of students who are still passive. This is aligned with research from Khoudri

(2024), which reveals that passive students do not mean they are lazy to speak, but because the tasks and learning strategies are not by their learning preferences.

Some previous studies are aligned with this study, where informants emphasized the importance of interesting learning methods and providing space for freedom of expression to students. Meanwhile, other informants emphasized learning strategies that create comfort in the classroom, such as motivating to learn first before starting the material. According to the informants, the right strategy can be implemented by recognizing the characteristics of students in the classroom. The main goal is to make the classroom comfortable and fun as a place to learn. Then, lecturers must apply learning strategies and methods that encourage the emergence of interaction between lecturers and students, not only about the material.

This study revealed that most students were interested in the role-play learning model where they were given the task of playing a role in the classroom. This result, supported by Korovina (as cited in Fitriani, 2025) shows that role play has a positive impact on students' willingness to communicate in speaking classes. This study is also aligned with research from Carrasco (as cited in Fitriani, 2025) which revealed that the characteristics of role play can encourage students to learn in a calm atmosphere so that students can achieve freedom of expression and voluntarily want to actively speak in class.

In addition, some students argue that the talk-active learning model is also interesting because they are given freedom of expression and have more room for opinions. The results of the interview are aligned with one of the types of communication strategies proposed by Lee and Ng (in Sari, 2016), namely *facilitator-oriented strategies* that emphasize the role of lecturers as facilitators in classroom discussions and student-oriented strategies that emphasize student involvement in conversations that occur during class by minimizing lecturer intervention.

Based on the results above, this study concludes that the crucial factor influencing students' willingness to communicate in speaking classes is having a friend as a conversation partner. Six out of ten informants stated that the situational factor that most influences the willingness to communicate is having a supportive interlocutor who is willing to provide feedback and does not laugh at mistakes; then this factor can influence other factors. This factor can create comfort in communication, thereby increasing the willingness to communicate. In addition, a very influential psychological factor is self-confidence. The best way to increase students' self-confidence is through thorough preparation and self-motivation, as well as motivation from friends and lecturers. The role of lecturers as a situational factor is also one of the crucial factors that can influence their WTC. Lecturers are considered motivators who always provide support and space for informants to speak. Researcher found that students feel calm when lecturers motivate them. Additionally, they hope that lecturers provide learning topics that they expect, as the type of topic also has a significant impact on their WTC for speaking in class. Therefore, lecturers and students must build a good relationship to achieve learning objectives.

This study also found new findings that contrast with previous studies. Based on the results of the study, lecturers are not the only crucial factor that can influence willingness to communicate. This is proven by several factors that are said to be the most influential, such as self-confidence, interlocutor, and discussion topics. This study also revealed that the assignments given by the lecturer do not influence students' willingness to communicate. This can be used

as further research to determine the type of assignments that are appropriate for students. Additionally, this study found that personality is not a major factor causing students to be reluctant to speak in class.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the ELESP students batch of 2022 still have complex factors influencing their willingness to communicate. They have not yet reached a comfortable point in speaking class, and some have not taken responsibility for learning and practicing to improve their willingness to communicate.

CONCLUSION

Several conclusions can be drawn from the research that has been conducted, namely that the willingness to communicate is the readiness of students to start communicating and speaking in language classes, especially English. To achieve the objectives of speaking classes, every student must have the willingness to communicate in order to be active and trained in speaking English in class.

However, there are still many students who do not have the willingness to speak in speaking classes, especially in professional context speaking classes, due to various factors such as psychological and situational factors. To identify the psychological and situational factors that influence students' willingness to communicate in speaking classes, it is necessary to hear students' voices to share their experiences in speaking classes, especially in professional context speaking classes.

Researcher can conclude that psychological indicators can be factors that influence students' willingness to communicate in speaking classes. It can be said that self-confidence and anxiety are psychological factors that were frequently complained about by students during interviews. Lack of self-

confidence was caused by classmates, grammar, experience, and a lack of English vocabulary. Similarly, anxiety is experienced by most students due to peers, classroom atmosphere, and English language proficiency.

Meanwhile, in situational indicators, there are factors that do not influence students' willingness to communicate at all, namely the type of task. This is different from other situational factors such as discussion topics, lecturer roles, classroom atmosphere, interlocutors, and lecturer strategies, which can have a significant influence on their willingness to communicate in speaking classes for professional contexts.

The analysis results also indicate that peers and instructors are the most significant factors in the situational indicators mentioned by many informants during the interviews. These two factors can influence various other factors. Therefore, students and instructors must collaborate to create mutually influential learning in speaking for professional contexts or other courses.

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